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INTEGRATING EXPLICIT AND IMPLICIT GRAMMAR LEARNING: A TBLT APPROACH TO PHRASAL VERBS

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ABSTRACT

This paper outlines a Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) approach for teaching phrasal verbs to upper-intermediate (B2) English as a Foreign Language (EFL) university students. The study begins with a detailed description of the target learners, their linguistic background, and learning preferences. It then justifies the selection of two academic texts, "Structure and Meaning in English" and "Linguistic Perspectives on English Grammar," as primary resources for understanding and teaching phrasal verbs. A comparative analysis of these texts is conducted, highlighting similarities and differences in their treatment of multi-word verbs, phrasal verbs, and prepositional verbs.

Keywords: Task-Based Language Teaching, grammar, morphological complexity, transitive, and intransitive clauses.

Introduction: The target learners study in the same group at the University of USWLU in the second course at the faculty of foreign philology. The group consists of 17 learners (ten females and seven males) and they are about 18-23 years old. Based on the university curriculum they have General English classes three times a week per intake. According to the requirements for university enrolment, nearly all of the learners got certificates indicating B2 level. Now learners are in the upper-intermediate level and moving to the advanced level. Target learners started to acquire comprehensive grammar knowledge from elementary school. Then they differently evolved their knowledge to reach this level. Previously, they have been exposed to simpler structures, as well as they moved to complicated ones.

Target learners were taught English grammar differently in the various stages of their language acquisition. Moreover, they acquired grammatical knowledge both explicitly and implicitly. They got explicit grammar instruction in the classroom

environment by being taught deductively the grammar structures. In such cases, their conscious awareness of grammar points evolved by noticing (Batstone, 1996). They acquired implicit instruction through unconscious awareness of the grammar rules, for example, through chatting on social sites in the target language, listening to TV programs, podcasts, and news, sharing experiences with the penal, etc. Meanwhile, such implicit grammar acquisition leads learners to utilize the structure appropriately in context without knowing the terminology and thinking about correct structuring (Larsen-Freeman et al., 2016). Despite achieving upper-intermediate level target learners still have stabilized errors that they fossilized in learners' speech and already become a grammatical habit (Cowan, 2008). They still make minor mistakes in different structures that this fossilization should be overcome through brief explanation and instruction. Furthermore, based on their interest and learning styles students mostly prefer to learn grammar through interactive activities, visual aids, media resources, online games, in class practical drills etc.

The primary reason for selecting these books I thought they are ideal for my target learners according to the following features:

- The books are written in academic English so that my learners at the B2 level can comprehend the context in standardized language.
- The books' main parts such as chapters, sections, and topics are highlighted in bold, and examples are in italics so that learners can scan and skim the necessary parts easily.
- The books offer extensive coverage of phrasal verbs, their definitions and examples. Examples are concise and suitable to my target learners. They provide several in-class practical activities to allow learners to get both explicit and implicit knowledge simultaneously in the language classroom.

Grammar topic exploration. The selected grammar books “Structure and Meaning in English: A Guide for Teachers” by Geraeme Kennedy and “Linguistic Perspectives on English Grammar: A Guide for EFL Teachers” by Martin Endley cover the topic of verb plus particles including multiple examples and explanations. The books will be beneficial to teach the target grammar topic to the learners as the content is comprehensible to the target learner's levels of proficiency (B2). The specific strength of these books is evaluated by their usefulness for learners who appreciate detailed explanations. Concerning similarity, the books introduce the verb construction at the

starting point generally, then move to specific aspects smoothly. Authors of the books analyze any verb and its correlation with different particles and vice versa. The approaches to explanation are also similar. Books are written based on a research-based approach and the explanations and opinions are justified with authentic examples.

Also, the books illustrate the topic verb plus particle splitting into three subtopics: multiword verbs, phrasal verbs and prepositional verbs. When it comes to differences Kennedy (2014) states that multi-word verbs, phrasal verbs and prepositional verbs have equal characteristics and they have the same function. Also, he indicates phrasal verbs can typically have the adverbial role and can be split from the verb, especially when there is a pronoun object. On the contrary, Endley (2007) states multi-word verbs can be divided into two types: phrasal verbs and prepositional verbs. On the other hand, Endley conducted deep research on multi-word verbs including their types, problems with form and meaning, and polysemy among multiword verbs in various contexts. Also the book “Linguistic Perspectives on English Grammar: A Guide for EFL Teachers” suggests several pedagogical implications on how to teach multi-word verbs in the classroom productively. Comparably, Endley (2007) indicates multi-word verbs as lexical units and they can be marked for tense and aspects, and function in either transitive or intransitive clauses. Kennedy (2014) focused on morphological features of the verb plus particle forms and investigated how different particles may influence the meaning of the verbs in different contexts.

While reading through the books I have identified several key terminologies to teach the selected topic more comprehensibly to target learners. For example, multi-word verbs, phrasal verbs, prepositional verbs, particle, semantic complexity, morphological complexity transitive and intransitive clauses, information structure and etc. After comparing the content of both sources I found the book “Linguistic Perspectives on English Grammar: A Guide for EFL Teachers” a better source to teach the topic of phrasal verbs to my learners at the B 2 level. Because the book includes more complicated explanations in detail and the narrative tone of the book is also more complex than another one. Moreover, in moving to the C1 level my target learners should be able to comprehend complex sentences and grammatical structures. The source offers several examples that demonstrate how phrasal verbs are used in different contexts. This might help learners understand the nuances and various methods by which phrasal verbs are used. The book is organized coherently and methodically,

facilitating learners in finding and accessing precise material about verb plus particle forms. It also focuses on accurate grammatical usage, which can help learners improve their comprehension and application of phrasal verbs.

TBLT Application.

Pre-Task.

Objective. Introduce the learners to the basic concept of phrasal verb and their function.

Teacher's instruction:

- ✦ Introduce the phrasal verbs using graphic representation (see Appendix 1)
- ✦ Provide precise explanations and definitions of phrasal verbs, highlighting the combinations of verbs and particles.
- ✦ Explain to students the common particles (e.g. off, up, at) and their meaning and function.
- ✦ Write down the whiteboard certain verbs (e.g. cut, break, give, look) and ask students to guess the appropriate particle to change their core meaning.

Task. Jigsaw storytelling

Objective. Practice the use of phrasal verbs in spoken context through storytelling activity [S, L, FF]

Teacher's instruction:

- ✦ Divide students into four groups
- ✦ Ask Group A to begin narrating a story, Group B, C, and D should continue. The process will continue in this circle till the time will be up [S, L]
- ✦ Ask each group to use at least two phrasal verbs in their sentences in each turn [FF] ▪ Monitor the storytelling process.
- ✦ Take notes on students' errors and explain the correct form at the end of the task.

Post Task

Objective. Identify the parts of phrasal verbs based on the meaning of the sentences from the text.

Teacher's instruction:

- ✦ Give students printed handouts illustrating gapped sentences (see Appendix 2).
- ✦ Ask students to sit in pairs

- ✦ Ask students to identify the omitted part of the phrasal verb (either verb or particle) suitable for the meaning of the sentence.
- ✦ Check students' answers, provide corrective feedback, and engage students in whole group discussion on their mistakes.

While designing Task Based Language Teaching I have consulted both forum-focused and meaning-focused instruction. According to Ellis (2018) learners communicate and work collaboratively around different tasks in TBLT that involve active collaboration and interaction. The book “Linguistic Perspectives on English Grammar: A Guide for EFL Teachers” is used to create authentic content for the graphic representation handouts. I have reviewed pages that illustrated phrasal verbs and collected suitable examples and represented them in graphics. In **the pre-task phase**, learners will be introduced to the phrasal verbs explicitly with the help of graphic representation. Because the target learners prefer to learn grammar rules through visual aids since they are

essential for visual comprehension. Also, a short activity will be held to check learners' comprehension.

The task phase focuses on the practical use of phrasal verbs through communicative activity. Hence I planned to implicate a jigsaw storytelling activity in order to stimulate my learners to use phrasal verbs in real- life contexts. The jigsaw storytelling activity involves participants adding their contributions to create collaborative stories that incorporate various ideas and views. This storytelling activity promotes creativity, collaboration, and the enhancement of narrative abilities. According to Storch (2018) communicative activities reinforce using explicit knowledge implicitly, which means learners will be able to apply their knowledge gained in forum-focused instruction through completing communicative activities as meaning-focused instruction.

Taking account of my learners' ages and levels I intended to develop gapped sentences for the **post-task** stage. As Ellis (2009, as cited in Güvendir & Hardacre, 2020) suggested production practice activities such as sentence transformation, gapped sentences, dialogues, drills, picture descriptions and others give the learners another chance in the post task stage to practice again the challenging grammatical forms until learners will be familiar with the structure. The gapped sentence will be completed by

working in pairs. Consequently, learners will be able to share their understanding of the topic.

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